

Figure S7. Enrichment analysis of proteins upregulated at symptom onset

Most relevant GO terms (pink bars) and KEGG pathways (gray bars) related to 73 proteins in serum-UpS, but not in Serum-UpPOS2 or Serum-UpNEG2. Bar length represents the significance of the specific gene set or term in the enrichment analysis using Enricher-KG.